

Case 1: information for teaching facilitator

This document describes the information that each role is given for case 1 (DP), as well as listing the “essential” roles that must be fulfilled when allocating roles to students.

Essential roles (must be allocated – denoted with #)

- MDM co-ordinator
- Endoscopist
- Radiologist
- Histopathologist
- Lower GI surgeon
- Oncologist

1) MDM Co-ordinator # (given to student 1)

“Case notes for DP

This 78 year old lady has presented to her GP with a change in her bowel habit for 6 weeks and 8kg weight loss in 2 months. General exam notes on the referral state: slim build, general and conjunctival pallor noted, abdominal examination demonstrated possible mass on the left side, no abnormality on digital rectal examination.

Consequently Mrs. P was referred on the 2 week wait cancer pathway.

So far she has had blood tests, colonoscopy, imaging and met the oncologist”

2) Endoscopist # (student 2)

“You carried out a flexible sigmoidoscopy and can report that you saw a large suspicious looking mass in the sigmoid colon. You took several biopsies and sent them for analysis. Given your experience you feel the mass would be suggestive of malignancy.”

<endoscopy image attached>

3) Radiologist # (student 3)

“On reviewing the CT images for Mrs. P you can report the following:

- There is a 5 cm x 6 cm mass, suspicious for malignancy in the sigmoid region
- The cancer has grown through the bowel wall (i.e. through the muscularis propria and into the subserosa)
- It appears to be affecting at least one but possibly 3 lymph nodes.
- It has not spread to other parts of the body i.e. no mets seen
- You would stage this cancer as T3bN1M0”

4) Histopathologist # (student 4)

“Blood tests for Mrs. P demonstrate microcytic anaemia suggestive of iron deficiency

Histology of biopsies from the endoscopy show an invasive epithelial tumour consistent with adenocarcinoma

You can offer to send these samples for testing for Lynch syndrome (if the group wishes)”

<histopathology image attached>

5) Lower GI surgeon # (student 5)

“You have not met Mrs. P yet. Consider the results you have been given including the TNM staging and her general health (WHO performance).

Your options for managing her condition are:

- Conservative – no surgery, refer back to oncologist for consideration of radiotherapy/chemotherapy
- Palliative surgery – e.g. advise a stent be fitted, non-curative but for symptom control
- Surgery (operate with curative intent) – e.g. total colectomy, pan proctocolectomy, hemicolectomy, sigmoid colectomy, anterior resection, abdominoperineal resection, ELAP, Hartmann’s procedure, loop colostomy, end colostomy, loop ileostomy, end ileostomy, ileo-anal pouch”

6) Oncologist # (student 6)

“You have met Mrs. P who was a very independent woman. Her bowel habit changes were intermittent PR bleeding and variation in stool types – sometimes loose (type 6/7) other times she felt constipated but there was no improvement with laxatives. She lives alone but has family living nearby. She mobilises with a stick. Apart from her PMH of hypertension which is managed on amlodipine, you consider her very fit and well. Mrs. P’s current knowledge is that she is being investigated with a high probability of colorectal cancer. Mrs. P wanted to consider all her options and has not ruled out anything.

Your options for management include:

- Watch and wait – no active treatment, recall for surveillance
- Conservative/Palliative – no curative intent to treatment, for symptomatic relief and preparation for end of life care
- Radiotherapy
- Chemotherapy”

7) Theatre/clinic co-ordinator (student 7)

“1 telephone consultation appointment – this week

2 Face 2 Face appointments – one this week, one next week

2 theatre slots – one this week, one in three weeks’ time”

8) Macmillan nurse (student 8)

“You have no previous knowledge of this patient

Possible usual resources you can offer are:

- Telephone support
- Group support sessions
- Leaflets/Educational material
- Counselling
- Visits to day centres/hospices
- Financial support”

9) Stoma nurse (student 9)

“You have no previous knowledge of this patient

You are not available this week for appointments

Possible usual resources you can offer are:

- Telephone support
- Face to face support e.g. if pt attends clinic
- Leaflets/Educational material
- Post op education/support”

10) Upper GI surgeon (student 10)

“No specific role in this scenario, however, given your surgical knowledge, you may be able to assist the lower GI surgeon in their treatment considerations for this patient.”